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Module 1. Strategic Context and Environmental Analysis

Learning Objective: To provide an understanding of the industry and macroeconomic environment in order to shape company strategy and mitigate external risks.

Topics:

1.1 Organization as a System. The concept of inputs (resources, finance), processes (construction and installation works), outputs (built facilities, profit). System metaphor (engine) and managing connections between departments.

Expected result: To understand your company as a system mechanism.

1.2 Environmental Analysis (PESTLE). External factors (Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Legal, Environmental). Identifying signs of crises (e.g., inflation, changes in building regulations, Green Deal in the EU).

Expected result: To be able to conduct a PESTLE analysis for a small construction company.

1.3 Digital Landscape and IT Assets. Why IT infrastructure (project management systems, mobile applications) is an important asset on par with machinery. W'N'R Example: mobile/web access to data, documents (and photo reports) in real time.

Expected result: To realize the role of digital tools in increasing control and reducing uncertainty.

1.4 Porter's Five Forces Model. Power of buyers, suppliers, competitors, new entrants, substitutes. Special characteristics of construction (low entry barriers, significance of reputation).

Expected result: To analyze the company's position among industry forces (e.g., why a small contractor is vulnerable).

1.5 Competitive Advantage. M. Porter: cost leadership, differentiation, focus. As applied to construction: examples of a "technological" approach (BIM, W'N'R transparency) and emphasis on quality/ecology. Practice: how "digital openness" through W'N'R makes a company attractive to large developers (transparency = reliability).

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Expected result: To determine which competitive advantage strategy the company should apply and how the W'N'R service strengthens differentiation.

1.6 Stakeholders and company resource management in a single digital environment.

Internal and external project participants: clients, investors, government authorities, contractors, and company employees. Definition of roles, interests, and influence level of project participants. Working with the expectations of different parties depending on market requirements and project specifics. Creating a company digital profile in the W'N'R system: filling in information about the company, contact details, specialization, resources, and project portfolio. Expected result: To identify key project participants and understand their role in company processes. To create and configure your company profile in the W'N'R system.

Module 2. Information Management and CDE (Common Data Environment)

Learning Objective: To teach how to use data as a strategic resource, building a common information environment of a project for scaling.

Topics:

2.1 Information as an Asset (DIKW). The DIKW model (Data->Information->Knowledge->Wisdom). Why "if you have the up-to-date drawing, you own the construction site". "Information swamp" during chaotic communication (WhatsApp).

Expected result: To understand the transition from data to knowledge, and the value of high-quality data.

2.2 Common Data Environment (CDE, ISO 19650). The principle of a "single source of truth". ISO 19650 standards: centralized document repository, version control, naming conventions. How W'N'R implements CDE: the "Knowledge Base" section is a single repository for all instructions, drawings, certificates. Example: absence of two versions of drawings due to the separation of access rights.

Expected result: To configure the CDE structure in W'N'R and maintain uniformity of documentation.

2.3 Communications Management (RFI, Transmittal, Submittal). Processes for official requests and transfer of information on a construction site. Why it is important to record requests in writing (not verbally).

Expected result: To develop a communications protocol: how to generate an RFI (formalized request for information) / transmittal (covering document).

2.4 Change Management. Recording deviations from the project - "variations" and claims. The principle of "we do not work for free": every change request is processed through the system. Introduction of justified changes into the cost estimate (CVR (Cost Value Reconciliation) see module 6). Digital footprint. All decisions, assignments, and approvals are carried out in W'N'R (through tasks, messages, documents). The project history is indisputable.

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Expected result: To create a new project in W'N'R: define roles (owner, manager, supervisor, worker), configure rights, upload document templates. To be able to manage changes and process them for payment.

2.5 Big Data in Construction. How accumulated data on past facilities (quantities, norms, labor inputs) in W'N'R helps calculate future projects.

Expected result: To realize the value of data; to be able to use simple forecasting methods (e.g., average productivity analysis).

Module 3. Organization and Personnel Management

Learning Objective: To build an effective organizational structure and corporate culture, ensure motivation and interaction without constant micromanagement.

Topics:

3.1 Organizational Structures. Functional, divisional, matrix. Advantages/disadvantages in the context of a growing construction firm. Why "a structure of 5 people falls apart at 50". Corporate culture.

Expected result: To be able to choose a suitable structure as the company grows and allocate authorities.

3.2 Group Dynamics (Tuckman). Team stages: forming, storming, norming, performing. Practical tips: how to "breeze through the storming stage" (team-building, rules on site).

Expected result: To apply knowledge of stages for managing a new crew and minimizing conflicts.

3.3 Motivation (cross-cultural). Theories of Maslow, Herzberg, Vroom's expectations. Nuances of motivation for field workers of different nationalities (relevant for EU/USA). How the multi-language support of W'N'R helps to understand each other.

Expected result: To analyze the needs of employees and select non-monetary incentives (recognition, career, conditions).

3.4 Leadership vs Management. Difference between leadership and management: a leader shapes a vision, engages and leads the team through changes; a manager ensures planning, organization, and control of work execution. Special characteristics of managing construction teams in conditions of a shortage of qualified specialists and high uncertainty. Flexible management approaches: adaptive planning, Agile approaches, and operational decision-making on site.

Expected result: To understand the difference between leadership and managerial functions and apply both approaches depending on the project situation.

3.5 Conflict Management. Harvard negotiation method (resolving "fires" without quarrels). Principles of conflict resolution (WIN - WIN).

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Expected result: To settle disagreements inside the organization and with contractors/clients constructively, protecting the company's interests.

3.6 Delegation and Control. What delegation is and what cannot be delegated. How to assign tasks through W'N'R and track their execution in real time.

Expected result: To learn how to "free the hands" of the manager: managing several facilities remotely through the system.

3.7 Collaborative Working (W'N'R). Work of distributed teams (office - construction site). W'N'R provides mobile communication, shared data access. Example: operational communication between a foreman and a project manager.

Expected result: To increase the interaction efficiency of office and field employees using the W'N'R system.

3.8 Role Model in W'N'R. Configuring roles (owner, manager, supervisor, worker, subcontractor) and areas of responsibility in the system.

Expected result: To correctly allocate access privileges so that information is protected and workers see only their own.

3.9 Performance Evaluation (KPI, W'N'R). How to collect objective metrics from the system (e.g., completed work volume, delays, material consumption).

Expected result: To use system data to motivate employees through bonuses/penalties.

Module 4. Operations Management (Production of Construction and Installation Works)

Learning Objective: To ensure stable and efficient operation of construction operations when scaling up the business.

Topics:

4.1 Business Process Engineering. Management circuit. Difference between one-off projects and periodic processes. Value Stream Mapping.

Expected result: To identify bottlenecks in construction: where "a brick gets stuck" on the way from request to laying.

4.2 Planning (WBS, Gantt). Breaking down a project into tasks (task tree) and deadlines. Principles of the critical path, buffers. W'N'R - as a necessary tool of the management circuit.

Expected result: To be able to create a baseline project plan. In W'N'R - to register key tasks with deadlines (Gantt chart).

4.3 Quality Management (TQM, ISO 9001). Deming Cycle (PDCA); "zero defects" culture. Cost of rework vs initial accuracy. Implementation of ISO 9001 standards (process documentation).

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Expected result: To develop a quality control system: acceptance of stages, compliance control. Use of W'N'R: photo-fixation of stages, checklists in Knowledge Base.

4.4 Supply Chain Management. Just-in-Time logistics, JIC, risks of delays. Working with subcontractors as partners. W'N'R allows planning procurement and controlling inventory ("Supplies" section).

Expected result: To reduce storage costs, prevent downtime due to material shortages, and optimize orders through the system.

4.5 Lean Construction. Searching for 8 types of waste (downtime, unnecessary movements, overproduction, etc.). How W'N'R provides resource utilization reports, identifying excess inventory, allowing to increase cost-efficiency in construction.

Expected result: To apply W'N'R tools to reduce waste: arranging a "waste hunt" (e.g., sharply reducing rebar surpluses, optimizing shifts).

4.6 Dispatching and Control (W'N'R). Monitoring daily reports (volumes, costs) in real time. Photo of hidden works - an independent objective arbiter of quality.

Expected result: To increase the speed of reaction to arising deviations without site visits.

4.7 Quality Control (W'N'R). Checking completed works for compliance with standards on site. Attaching photos and comments to a task, recording defects.

Expected result: To use the system for remote quality audit (marking problematic areas on photos).

Module 5. B2B Marketing and Sales

Learning Objective: To acquire and select high-quality contracts using instrumental knowledge of marketing and digital technologies.

Topics:

5.1 Market Segmentation and Niche Targeting. Dividing construction into residential, infrastructural, industrial; difference between general contracting and highly specialized contractors.

Expected result: To determine the most profitable niche for oneself (considering competition and margin), to give up a "mountain of tenders for everything at once".

5.2 Competitive Strategies (Porter). Three paths: costs, differentiation, focus. Examples in construction (fast construction vs innovative technologies). W'N'R supports differentiation - the system as part of a "reliable contractor" reputation.

Expected result: To match one's position and choose a strategy.

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5.3 Marketing Mix 7P (services). Product (type of facility), Price (tender policy), Place (geography of works), Promotion (reputation, promotion), People (team expertise), Process (BIM / W'N'R - quality), Physical evidence (construction site quality, demonstration of reliability).

Expected result: To build a marketing campaign for a specific segment (e.g., "Leadership in Quality"). To indicate the role of W'N'R in improving processes and increasing client trust.

5.4 Knowledge Base as a Portfolio. Using the archive of completed works in the system as evidence of experience during client pre-qualification.

Expected result: To arrange a knowledge base in W'N'R: upload the best photos of facilities, work completion certificates, credentials - in order to back up commercial proposals with real data.

Module 6. Financial Management and Accounting

Learning Objective: To learn financial planning and control of income/expenses in construction projects.

Topics:

6.1 Fundamentals of Financial Accounting. Three key reports: balance sheet (assets/liabilities), P&L (services - expenses), Cash Flow (Statement of Cash Flows). Difference between profit vs cash balance. What a cash gap is. How to prepare a Statement of Cash Flows, see a cash gap.

Expected result: To understand that profit can be on paper while there is no cash (and how to avoid a cash gap).

6.2 Cost Value Reconciliation (CVR). Reconciliation of planned costs with actual costs for each stage (part of Earned Value Management). How to create a profit "X-ray" in W'N'R.

Expected result: To monthly analyze real cost compared to planned cost in order to identify overruns and react in a timely manner.

6.3 Accounting for Volume of Construction and Installation Works. Linking completed works (by tasks/reports in W'N'R) to the project financial plan.

Expected result: Based on the entered W'N'R data, draft certificates are generated (simulating invoicing), saving office time.

6.4 Progress Billing. Application for Payment and Interim Payment Certificate (IPC) in FIDIC/NEC contracts.

Expected result: To be able to form applications for intermediate payments in accordance with European procedures to minimize cash gaps.

6.5 Budgeting and Forecasting. Compiling a project budget and forecasting the final cost (Estimate at Completion). Variance analysis (e.g., due to rising material prices).

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Expected result: To compile and adjust the budget, analyze if it is "drifting" due to inflation or errors in the cost estimate.

6.6 Connection of Work Volumes and Financial Accounting. The W’N’R system uses a cost estimates section containing work volumes and their cost, as well as functionality for tracking work execution progress. Based on the entered volumes and execution status, control of actually completed works and their cost is ensured for the subsequent generation of financial documents and reporting.

Expected result: To show data from W’N’R (completed tasks and materials) as a source of indisputable data for financial reports.

6.7 Accounts Receivable Management. Control of timely certification and payments. Why there is profit but no cash. A problem in the construction business - a company can be profitable on paper and simultaneously experience a shortage of cash. Overdue accounts receivable as a hidden credit to the client - when a contractor does not control payment, they begin to fund the project at their own expense.

Expected result: To understand why a profitable construction company can experience a shortage of cash; to distinguish between profit, Cash Flow, and accounts receivable; to identify the causes of cash gaps in construction projects; to build a control process for certification and payments; to control the movement of money from work execution to receipt of payment; to identify problem areas in the "work execution - certificate - invoice - payment" chain; to reduce the risk of losing money due to unsigned volumes and unrecorded changes; to implement regular control of accounts receivable across projects; to use digital tools and W’N’R to record completed works and confirm volumes; to increase the financial stability of the company through transparency of processes and reduction of overdue payments.

Course structure by modules

Course 1: From Craft to Industry					
Module 1: Strategy / PESTLE / Porter	Module 2: Digital Management / CDE	Module 3: Organization / Personnel	Module 4: Operations / Lean / SQM	Module 5: Marketing & Sales	Module 6: Finance / Budget